

Focus Groups Questions Guide (With Bangladeshi Female Farmers)

Objectives:

1. *Ratios of Bangladeshi female farmers' values reflected in existing agriculture apps.*
2. *Strategies to address Bangladeshi female farmers' values in agriculture mobile apps.*

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Approximate duration: 60-90 minutes

Introduction (By the researcher) and an Icebreaker session

1. Introducing myself (researcher)
2. Explaining the research project
3. Explaining the focus groups structure
4. Giving the explanatory statement
5. Getting the consent form signed by the participants

General Questions

1. What kind of farming do you do?
2. How long have you been working as a farmer?

Values Probing Questions

1. What do you do? How do you earn?
2. Other than your job, what do you like to do?
3. What are the most important things to do in your life?
4. What are your hope and dreams?
5. What would you like to see for your children?
6. What kind of facilities do you need that will be beneficial for farming?
7. What are the goals to achieve in your life?

Questions on Values in Apps

1. Do you use mobile apps for farming purposes? If yes, what are the names of the apps?
2. What kind of help do you usually take from the apps?
3. What changes did the apps make in your life?
4. Can you recall any feature that you think made your life better? If yes, why do you think it is impactful?
5. To what extent do the apps meet your requirements?
6. What are the difficulties/ challenges you face while using the apps?

Questions on Strategies to Address values in Apps

1. What particular features do you expect from the apps?
2. How do you give feedback of the apps? Did you ever write reviews to give feedback of the apps?

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3. Who comes to collect your feedback? How do they collect it?
4. What suggestions do you have to make the agriculture apps more usable for you?